

The Effect of Internal Gravity Waves on Cloud Evolution in Substellar Atmospheres

I. BACKGROUND

Fig. 1: The Surface map of the Luhman 16B. (Crossfield et al. 2014)

Substellar objects exhibit photometric variability, believed to be caused by processes such as magnetically-driven spots or inhomogeneous cloud coverage.

Recent models suggest that turbulent flows (Helling et al. 2001, A&A 376, 194–212) and atmospheric waves may play an important role in dust cloud evolution (Freytag et al. 2010, A&A, 513, A19).

- What is the effect of internal gravity waves on dust cloud evolution?
- Can observation of resulting cloud structures be used to recover atmosphere parameters?

II. FLUID MODEL

We use a linear vorticity ζ stream-function ψ fluid model.

- Waves driven from the domain's centre by an oscillating, gaussian perturbation of density ρ_A ;

- Eqs. (1), (2) solved using leapfrog;

- Eq. (3) solved using Successive Over-Relaxation.

$$\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial t} = -\frac{g}{\rho_0} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \rho_0}{\partial y} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} \quad (2)$$

$$\zeta = -\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2: Equilibrium atmospheric profile used for simulations.

($T_{\text{eff}} = 1500\text{K}$, $\log g = 5.0$) brown dwarf data obtained from Drift-Phoenix atmosphere model (Hauschildt & Baron 1999; Helling+ 2004; Helling & Woitke 2006; Witte+ 2009, 2011) and additional data from Rodríguez-Barrera+ (2018)

Core Findings

(1)

Internal Gravity Waves in brown dwarf model atmospheres propagate along an x-shaped pattern and create banded areas of perturbed density, pressure and temperature.

(2)

Increased densities and temperatures raise the thermal velocity of the gas, causing a weaker but non-negligible increase of the dust mantle growth rate.

(3)

The relative impact of Internal Gravity Waves on dust nucleation is stronger in warm, TiO_2 -poor brown dwarfs.

Fig. 3: plots of density (top), nucleation (middle) and mantle growth (bottom) responses to a range of perturbation frequencies and amplitudes

Fig. 5: plots of density (top), nucleation (middle) and mantle growth (bottom) responses to a range of perturbation frequencies and amplitudes

III. DUST MODEL

The nucleation rate J_* and mantle growth rate γ are derived from Gail+ (1984); Helling+ (2001); Stark+ (2018):

$$J_* = \frac{n_x}{\tau} Z \exp \left[(N_* - 1) \ln S - \left(\frac{T_\Theta}{T} \right) \frac{N_* - 1}{(N_* - 1)^{1/3}} \right]$$

$$\gamma = \frac{f_x \rho_{\text{gas}} v_{\text{rel},x}}{4 \rho_{\text{dust}}}$$

With:

- n_x the number density of the dust species,
- N_* the size of the critical cluster,
- τ the dust settling timescale,
- S the supersaturation ratio,
- $v_{\text{rel},x}$ the thermal equilibrium velocity of the gas.

Fig. 4: vertical 2D map of a gravity wave's density perturbation. $\omega = 0.25 N$, $\rho_A = 0.2 \rho_0$

Key	Model	Teff	log(g)
BD	Typical brown dwarf	1500K	5.0
TD	T dwarf	1200K	4.5
LD	L dwarf	2000K	4.5
LGTD	Low-gravity L draws	1200K	3.0
LGLD	Low-gravity T dwarf	2000K	3.0

IV. OBSERVATIONAL DIAGNOSTICS

We link the governing equations of internal gravity waves to observable characteristics through the waves' dispersion relation:

$$\omega^2 = -\frac{g}{\rho_0} \frac{\partial \rho_0}{\partial y} \cos^2 \Theta$$

$$\rho_0 \propto f(\Delta y, \Delta m, g, \omega, J_*)$$

With Δm the difference in apparent magnitude between a wave's peaks and troughs, and Δy the wave's apparent spatial wavelength.

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